

CHOOSING TOOLS FOR MECHANISING THE LOADING AND LOWERING WORKS

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Abstract: This article provides information and recommendations on the selection of means of mechanization of lifting and lowering operations.

Key words: loading machines, mechanism, blocks, pulleys, mobile cranes, cargo, economic benefits.

Selecting the type of loading and unloading machines and mechanisms means determining and evaluating their technical, operational and environmental qualities in order to use them with high efficiency. Such choices often depend on the methods of mechanization at a particular point, that is, specific conditions and technological processes [1].

Loading and unloading operations can be divided into small and large mechanization [2,3].

In the small mechanization of loading and unloading operations, simple mechanisms and various devices (blocks, pulleys, mobile cranes operated by hand, equipment mounted on moving carts) are used. Small mechanization of loading and unloading works is different and differs from each other by the use of one or another simple equipment or set of mechanisms [4,5,6]. In road transport, there are often pick-up and drop-off points with a small cargo turnover. In such points, from an economic point of view, it is appropriate to use high-performance, complex and expensive machines and mechanisms, as well as small mechanization equipment [7].

In large-scale mechanization of loading and unloading operations, high-performance, stationary and mobile complex loading machines and mechanisms are usually used instead of small mechanization equipment [8,9,10]. It is desirable to use large mechanization at loading and unloading points with a constant, mass stable turnover of goods (at large railway stations, water basins, ports and stations, large warehouses, large industrial enterprises) [11,12,13,14]. When choosing lifting and lowering machines and mechanisms, it is necessary to take into account their high efficiency. High productivity depends on proper organization of work [15,16,17]. When choosing loading machines and

mechanisms, it is necessary to take into account the type of loads and the nature of loading and unloading operations, the weight, shape, characteristics of the load, the power of the selected machines and mechanisms, and the possibility of using them in certain objects [18,19,20].

It is important to take into account the amount of capital and current operating expenses when choosing loading machines and mechanisms and organizing loading and unloading operations. Of course, the above-mentioned costs are primarily related to the economic benefits obtained from all loading operations in the transport process. However, it is necessary not to forget the social issues related to the mechanization of heavy work [21,22].

The mechanisms used in all loading and unloading operations can be divided into three main groups: stationary (immovable), mobile and types installed on vehicles [23,24]. It is desirable to use stationary mechanisms at points with a large mass and stable load turnover, as there are more opportunities to use them efficiently.

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